

Development of a Deliberative Civic Values Index Observational Checklist

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Introduction

This technical report documents the rationale and development process underlying the Larpocracy Observational tool for deliberative engagement. The tool builds on previous work on subjective measures of deliberative civic values, but focusses on observable actions of participants in a larp or larp-adjacent event. It provides a structured way to document how players engage in deliberation during a larp event.

The observation tool is planned to exist in multiple versions, both suitable for documenting events ongoing activities, and for analyzing video-recorded larp sessions. Both versions can be used for both online and physical larp sessions.

Purpose of observation protocol

There are two main uses of the tool. The first use is as a tool to evaluate if a particular larp design is successful in fostering deliberative engagement. The second use is to observe differences in engagement between different runs of the same larp, or differences in engagement between players in the same run. Larp events can develop in very different ways even when based on the same larp design. Many factors contribute to this effect, such as who participates, the social dynamics between players and between players and facilitators, and external factors such as when and where the larp is run and how players were recruited. Hence, the tool can aid in understanding unexpected effects that emerge in a particular run of a larp, or explain differences in the player experience between players in the same run.

Theory background

This work is grounded in the theory of Deliberative Civic Values proposed by Julia Jennstål, Katrin Uba, and PerOla Öberg (2021). This theory posits that the extent to which citizens subscribe to deliberative civic values is vital for a healthy deliberative democratic system. In the work by Jennstål et al, a questionnaire-based measure operationalizing deliberative civic values was developed. This tool is included in the quantitative survey tools used in Larpocracy.

In Jennstål et al, a factor analysis of survey responses to the questionnaire revealed four underlying factors *reasoning*, *listening*, *reflecting*, and also a *non-deliberative rhetorical* value. *Reasoning* refers to participants' willingness to state, explain, and justify their views. *Listening* means paying equal attentive attention to all other participants. *Reflecting* involves the readiness to rethink initial views and ideas in continuous deliberation. And *non-deliberate* rhetorical value refers to framing the conversation as an attempt to argue convincingly for one's own opinion and to win the debate.

The observation protocol was developed with these four concepts as a basis. However, the protocol aims to capture *behaviours* rather than individual values. For multiple reasons, it should not be assumed that the individual attitudes and the observed behaviour of the same person will indicate the same underlying factor. Rather, the observation protocol could potentially be used as a tool to investigate if there is any correlation between values and behaviour. This, however, is future work that falls outside the scope of Larpocracy.

Development Process

This work started by identifying reliable behavioural observational indicators and further integrates them with suitable observation strategies to create the tools used in the actual larp study. The process unfolded through four phases. The first phase involves a literature review, through which an initial pool of observational indicators was built by drawing on existing frameworks from deliberation research and related fields. The second phase consists of iterative development, in which the indicators were applied to pre-recorded larp materials and refined through a series of internal-testing rounds. The third phase involves a reliability evaluation workshop, where the indicators were further assessed for inter-observer reliability. The fourth stage adapts the indicators to actual research needs, allowing different researchers to assemble the indicators and apply different observation strategies to create tailored observation checklists or agreements.

Phase 1: Building the observation indicators pool

The aim of this phase was to explore potential behavioural indicators for capturing deliberative values, grounded in the four key concepts of deliberative civic values proposed by Jennstål et al. (2021): *reasoning*, *listening*, *reflecting*, and *non-deliberative* behaviour. For each dimension, relevant literature was drawn to inform the identification of observable indicators.

For the *reasoning* dimension, the focus primarily drew on Stomer-Galley's (2007) coding scheme for assessing the quality of political deliberations in both face-to-face and online settings. This work largely grounded in conversation analysis, looking into participants' spoken contribution during the deliberations. For the *listening* dimension, the review partly drew on non-verbal cues as observable indicators for accessing the quality of attentive or active listening. Including *eye gaze* (Vertegaal, 2001), *note-taking* (Smith et al., 2013), *response token* (Gardner, 2001), *nodding* (Tanaka et al., 2018), *emotional response* (Bavelas et al., 2000) and *motor mimicry* (Bavelas et al., 2000). In addition, certain forms of participants' spoken contributions can also serve as indicators of attentive listening, such as *topic continuity* (Stomer-Galley, 2007), *paraphrase* (Bodie et al., 2007). The *non-deliberative* dimension was largely informed by the observational model developed by Haug et al. (2008) for the comparative evaluation of deliberative events. This model proposes a three-dimensional analytical framework, from which the current work adopted the dimension of *hard power behaviour* and *competitive behaviour*. In addition, several indicators were incorporated to further enrich the definition, including *Rhetoric question asking* (Stomer-Galley, 2007); *interruption*, *floor holding* behavior proposed by Gabriel et al. (2002) for assessing the quality of participatory design. As for *reflecting* dimension, this phase did not identify clear behavioural indicators that could be used during the observation.

Phase 2: Iterative refinement of indicators

This phase focused on adjusting the indicators set by refining their descriptions and merging overlapping ones. To ensure that the indicators could be applied in different contexts, two sets of larp materials were collected and tested through observational practice. The materials consisted of video recordings from *The Committee* (Bowman et al., 2024) and *The Assembly* (Bowman et al., 2025), both of which are

deliberative style larp scenarios. These recordings covered both in-person and online settings (via Zoom) and involved participants with different levels of larp experience.

The observation practices were conducted in ELAN, a professional tool for multimodal annotation of audio and video recording, using two different observation strategies. The first strategy followed a time-aligned video-annotation approach, in which the observer annotated the recording in ELAN by marking the exact time intervals during which behaviours corresponding to each indicator were observed. The second strategy was inspired by the Classroom Observation Protocol for Undergraduate STEM (COPUS) developed by Smith et al. (2013), which is a lived observation protocol designed to assess classroom behaviours of both students and instructors. It was based on a time-sampling approach, in which observers noted whether behaviours corresponding to each indicator occurred within each two-minute interval. This strategy was adopted because it helped to reduce observer fatigue and showed potential for adaptation to live observation settings. In this study, the length of the time intervals was adjusted to a shorter duration of 10-15 seconds to capture a denser set of behavioural data. Within each interval, observers recorded whether the relevant behaviours had occurred.

The indicators set went through three interactive refinement cycles to arrive at the final version used for the following testing. All modifications and their rationales were documented in the iteration logs to ensure traceability.

Phase 3: Inter-observer reliability evaluation

The purpose of this phase was to assess whether the indicators developed in the previous stages could be applied consistently and understood by different observers. Therefore, a workshop was held to examine the inter-observer reliability of the indicators. It lasted for seven hours and took place in an enclosed meeting room at Ekonomikum, Uppsala University. The workshop was hosted by a researcher from the research team and conducted with two participants as independent observers recruited from the Human-Computer Interaction master's programme at Uppsala University. They were selected due to their prior experience in user research. The workshop consisted of three phases: (1) an introduction to the observation codebook, (2) a calibration session, and (3) an independent observation session.

The first introductory phase aimed to familiarize participants with the codebook developed from the latest version of the iteratively refined indicator set. It included a detailed explanation of the indicators with examples, as well as an introduction to the observation strategy used during the workshop. During the session, participants were able to ask questions at any time, and the entire session was recorded for later reference.

The second-phase calibration session aimed to allow participants to practice applying the observation protocol introduced in the previous session. It also served to clarify remaining uncertainties and to reach consensus on potential mismatches of the interpretation between participants. A five-minute larp recording was provided together with the necessary tools, including the observation checklists and a computer with ELAN installed. The larp material used in this calibration session was selected from a different larp scenario than the material later provided for the independent observation session. Participants reviewed the materials together and discussed which behavioural indicators should be

recorded within each observational interval. During the session, participants were also able to ask questions at any time, and the researcher might correct any errors that occurred, such as misinterpretations of indicators, misuse of the checklist, or misuse of the observation strategy and so on.

The final session served the purpose of collecting data to examine the consistency of the observation protocol by comparing the coding results between two participants. Two 20-minute larp recordings were provided sequentially to the participants, with the materials presented in different orders to avoid order effects. Both recordings were selected from the first 20-minute in-game segments of the deliberative larps *The Committee* (Bowman et al., 2024) and *The Assembly* (Bowman et al., 2025), and participants were required to observe three of the players individually. The necessary materials were provided, including the observation checklists, a computer with ELAN installed, larp recordings pre-edited into multiple 15-second intervals within ELAN, and a printed version of the codebook. Before the observation of each material began, participants were given printed instructions introducing the context, specifying whom to observe, and other necessary information of the larp. There were no time limitations, and participants were allowed to replay the recordings until they felt confident in their coding.

After the evaluation workshop, the coding result from the two observers were digitalized by the researcher and compared to assess inter-observer reliability using Cohen's Kappa, and occurrence rates. The results are presented in the *indicators and reliability* section.

Phase 4: Observation tool development

Based on the needs of the research, the results were further developed into observation protocols tailored to different analytical purposes. Protocol 1 was designed for live observation, aiming to guide observers' attention towards noticing and capturing valuable deliberative moments during larp events. Protocol 2 was designed for recording-based analysis with a stronger focus on quantification, enabling the examination of the distribution of deliberation-related behaviours across the larp session.

Result

In this section, we present the indicator set and the results of the evaluation, together with the two observation protocols developed for different research purposes.

Indicators and reliability

The observation indicators were divided into two perspectives: *speaker*, capturing behaviours while a player is speaking; and *listener*, capturing behaviours while the player was in others' speaking turns. The set comprised 18 indicators: 8 exclusive to the speaker perspective (*Social Talk, Facilitation, Opinion, Sourcing Elaboration, Genuine Question, Logical Elaboration, Topic Continuity, and Clarification*), 8 exclusive to the listener perspective (*Nodding, Verbal Response, Notes Taking, Interruption, Emotional*

Expression, Gaze, and Motor Mimicry), and 2 applicable to both (*Competition Behaviour and Hard Power Behaviour*). Brief definitions are further presented in the table below.

Role	Indicator	Code	Definition
Speaker	Social talk	SOCL	Utterances that express thoughts not directly related to the topic of deliberation, serving primarily social or relational purpose.
	Facilitation	FAC	Process-oriented utterances that regulate or coordinate the flow of discussion.
	Opinion	OPI	Opinion is utterance that presents a clear claim or idea.
	Sourcing Elaboration	SEL	Defined as the utterance when the speaker uses interpersonal or external reference to support an argument.
	Genuine Question	GQ	Utterance when the speaker seeks information from others.
	Logical Elaboration	LEL	Defined as utterance where the speaker expands an argument based on logical, hypothetical reasoning, or value justification.
	Topic Continuity	TPC	Coded when the speaker maintains topic continuity
	Competition Behaviour	CB	When the participants displays behaviour that is oriented toward winning the discussion:
	Clarification	CLAR	Clarification is utterance when the speaker tries to clarify the expression of their prior expression or opinion.
	Hard Power Behaviour	HB	When the participants display hard power behaviour, such as threatening and demanding.
Listener	Nodding	NOD	When the listener responds to the speaker with head movement
	Verbal Response	VEB	When the listener produces short verbal phrases to the speaker.
	Notes taking	NT	When the listener writes or types notes related to the discussion. Can happen in both impersonal and online conditions.
	Interruption	INT	When the listener interrupts another speaker's speaking turn, as a way to draw attention away from the current speaker.
	Emotional Expression	EME	When the listener reacts to the speaker through facial expression.
	Gaze	GAZ	When the listener maintains gaze toward the speaker (>2s).
	Motor Mimicry	MM	When the listener mirrors or synchronizes with the speaker's expressions, gestures, or movements.

Listener	Competition Behaviour	CB	When the participants display behaviour that is oriented toward winning the discussion:
	Hard Power Behaviour	HB	When the participants display hard power behaviour, such as threatening and demanding.

Two observers independently coded two 20-minute larp recording. The recordings were pre-edited into 15-second intervals, resulting in a total of 160 observation intervals. From these, 160 data were collected from the *speaker* perspective, while 403 observations data were collected from the *listener* perspective, as players functioned solely as speaker in some turns. Inter-observer reliability was then examined using Cohen's Kappa and occurrence rates. The results are presented in the following table.

Role	Indicator	n	Kappa (IRR)	Approx. Sig.	Occur rate-CoderA	Occur rate-CoderB
Speaker	Facilitation	160	0.858	0	16.25%	15.00%
	Social talk	160	0.503	0	8.75%	3.13%
	Opinion	160	0.361	0	35.00%	43.13%
	Sourcing Elaboration	160	0.177	0.009	51.88%	26.25%
	Genuine Question	160	0.139	0.139	9.38%	8.13%
	Logical Elaboration	160	0.006	0.935	11.88%	10.00%
	Topic Continuity	160	-0.203	0.01	16.25%	17.50%
	Competition Behaviour	160	-0.042	0.579	5.63%	3.13%
	Clarification	160	/	/	0.00%	2.50%
	Hard Power Behaviour	160	/	/	0.00%	0.00%
Listener	Nodding	403	0.354	0	36.48%	19.85%
	Verbal Response	403	0.193	0	1.74%	5.21%
	Notes taking	403	0.143	0.001	6.20%	14.39%
	Interruption	403	0.242	0	0.99%	0.99%
	Emotional Expression	403	0.074	0.054	34.24%	10.42%
	Gaze	403	0.047	0.114	91.56%	54.09%

Motor Mimicry	403	/	/	0.00%	0.00%
Competition Behaviour	403	/	/	0.00%	0.00%
Hard Power Behaviour	403	/	/	0.00%	0.00%

Overall, most indicators exhibited low Cohen’s Kappa values. Only *Facilitation* (Kappa = 0.858) and *Social Talk* (Kappa = 0.503) achieved higher levels of agreement, corresponding to substantial (Kappa > 0.80) and moderate (Kappa > 0.40) agreement respectively. However, these indicators are not central to capturing deliberative values. The indicators *Opinion* (Kappa = 0.361) and *Nodding* (Kappa = 0.354) showed comparatively better performance among the deliberation-related indicators, reaching fair agreement (Kappa > 0.20). Several indicators exhibited poor agreement, including *Logical Elaboration*, *Topic Continuity*, *Gaze*, *Emotional Expression*, and *Competition Behaviour* (speaker). Meanwhile, several indicators were not observed during this coding session. These indicators primarily relate to non-deliberative behaviour, including *Hard Power Behaviour*, *Competition Behaviour* (listener), as well as other aspects such as *Motor Mimicry* and *Clarification*.

Such result indicates the need for further refinement of the indicators. Due to the time constraints, participant received only 1.5 hours of training to become familiar with the indicators. During the post-session interviews, both participants reported that the second recording was easier to observe than the first, despite receiving the materials in different orders. It is expected that additional training sessions would further improve inter-observer reliability. Several indicators were found to present distinct challenges and therefore require further revision. The *Logical Elaboration* is reported as too ambitious to identify. The *Gaze* indicator was particularly difficult to apply in the online setting, as the direction of participants’ gaze are difficult to identify whether it aim toward the Zoom interface. *Emotional Response* was also reported to be too subtle and highly individual, making is difficult to identify consistency across observers. For *Topic Continuity*, affecting by the fact that players often referred to each other implicitly, and that topics could have been introduced several speaking turns earlier, making it difficult to trace. For indicators that were not observed or only rarely observed, additional larp recordings are required to examine whether they should be retained in the protocol and to provide more examples to support observer training.

Observation protocol 1: Live observation checklist

Currently, a version of the observation protocol has been specialized for observing one specific larp, *the Assembly*. In this section, we present the generic protocol. For the live observation version, to reduce observer fatigue during live observation, the indicator set was further combined into a set of main indicator categories, with the original indicators and examples serving as cues to support observers’ work. Following the structure of speaker and listener, the speaker perspective comprises the following main categories: *Opinion with Reasoning*, *Opinion with Evidence*, *Relating Opinion to Others*, *Verbal Response*, and *Competitive Behaviour*; the listener perspective includes *Positive Non-Verbal Response*, *Negative Non-Verbal Reaction*, and *Dismissive Non-Verbal Response*.

The generic observation checklists are presented in Technical Report Appendix I. The unit of analysis is defined as a speaking turn, starting from the moment a player begins speaking to the end of the utterance. Coding is conducted for each speaking turn. Observers are required to mark the corresponding indicator category using a simple symbol such as “√” or “|” in the coding area (B and C in Figure 1). Observers should record each indicator only once per speaking turn, even if the corresponding behaviour occurs multiple time during that turn. The definition of the indicator also presents on the checklist (A in Figure 1) for observers’ reference. Coding at the level of main categories is required (B in Figure 1), while coding at the level of sub-categories is encouraged (C in Figure 1).

A						
Behavior	Code	Category	Sub-category	Participant 5	Participant 6	
Opinion stating-1 (contributing a speech act)	OPI-REAS	Opinion with Reasoning	Logical reasoning: 1) Neutral (NEU): statement expressing a new idea. 2) Hypothetical reasoning (HYP): the elaboration where participants present their opinion by constructing an imagined or conditional situation, exploring possible outcomes and consequences. Such statements often begin with expressions like “if...” “imagine...” “what if...” 3) Value justification (VJ): the elaboration in which participants justify their opinion based on their personal values or judgements. Often started by “I am afraid...” “I fear...” “I prefer...” “For me, what matters is...” 4) Clarification (CLAR): includes statements that explain, refine or make explicit a previously stated opinion.	Logical reasoning: ✓✓✓	Logical reasoning: ✓✓✓✓	B
			NEU: ✓ HYP: ✓ VJ: ✓ CLAR:	NEU: ✓ HYP: ✓ VJ: ✓ CLAR:	C	
	OPI-EVI	Opinion with Evidence	Sourced evidence: 1) Personal experience (PER): the elaboration includes personal experience, such as personal stories, first hand accounts, accounts of close friends or family members. 2) Material / documents (MAT): the elaboration includes references to the bridging documents, both implicit or explicit. Often signal as “According to the application...” “In the document they said...” Including statements of absence of or problems with the facts in the provided documents. 3) Other participants (OTH): the elaboration includes referring back to the opinion from other participants or prior comments in the discussion. This must be an explicit reference, such as “Like what Maria said...” 4) Mass media (MM): the elaboration includes explicit references to the mass media (newspaper, internet, social media, advertisement, etc.)	Sourced evidence: ✓✓✓✓	Sourced evidence: ✓	B
			PER: ✓ MAT: ✓ OTH: ✓ MM: ✓	PER: ✓ MAT: ✓ OTH: ✓ MM:	C	

Figure 1. Observation checklist for Protocol 1: usage instructions

Observation protocol 2: Protocol for observing recorded material

The indicator set used for Protocol 2 was the same as that used in the evaluation workshop. The observation checklist is presented in Appendix II. The unite of analysis is defined as a fixed 15-second time interval, representing as a row in the observation checklist. Within each observation interval, observers record the data in binary form, with “√” indicating presence and blank indicating absence of the corresponding behaviour.

During the observation, observer should first define the owner of the speaking turn by marking down player’s id in area A (Figure 2). The player who speaks the longest duration within each interval is defined as the owner. Area B and C indicate the coding area for the *speaker* and *listener* perspectives, respectively. Observers mark “√” in the corresponding cell if the behavior occurs within the intervals. During the observation, participants were able to control video playback and pause as needed and could replay if necessary.

A		B										C							
Time interval		Speaker										Listener							
												Participant: <i>A</i>							
No.	own	SOCL	FA	OPI	SEL	LEL	TPC	CB	HB	GAZ	NT	NOD	EME	INT	VEB	CB	HB		
1	<i>A</i>		✓																
2	<i>A</i>			✓	✓														
3	<i>C</i>			✓			✓			✓		✓							
4	<i>D</i>			✓			✓								✓				
5	<i>D</i>					✓				✓				✓					
6	<i>D</i>	✓								✓									
7	<i>E</i>			✓		✓				✓									
8	<i>E</i>				✓					✓		✓							
9	<i>A</i>	✓																	
10	<i>A</i>			✓			✓												

Figure 2. Observation checklist for Protocol 2: usage instruction

Note

A more in-depth reflection on how the protocol captures deliberative value will be discussed in an upcoming article.

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Technical report Appendix I. Observation checklist for protocol 1

Behavior	Code	Category	Sub-category	Participant 5	Participant 6	Participant 7	Participant 8
Opinion stating-1 (contributing a speech act)	OPI-REAS	Opinion with Reasoning	Logical reasoning: 1) Neutral (NEU): statement expressing a new idea. 2) Hypothetical reasoning (HYP): the elaboration where participants present their opinion by constructing an imagined or conditional situation, exploring possible outcomes and consequences. Such statements often begin with expressions like "if..." "imagine..." "what if..." 3) Value justification (VJ): the elaboration in which participants justify their opinion based on their personal values or judgements. Often started by "I am afraid..." "I fear..." "I prefer..." "For me, what matters is..." 4) Clarification (CLAR): includes statements that explain, refine or make explicit a previously stated opinion.	Logical reasoning: NEU: HYP: VJ: CLAR:	Logical reasoning: NEU: HYP: VJ: CLAR:	Logical reasoning: NEU: HYP: VJ: CLAR:	Logical reasoning: NEU: HYP: VJ: CLAR:
	OPI-EVI	Opinion with Evidence	Sourced evidence: 1) Personal experience (PER): the elaboration includes personal experience, such as personal stories, first hand accounts, accounts of close friends or family members. 2) Material / documents (MAT): the elaboration includes references to the bridging documents, both implicit or explicit. Often signal as "According to the application..." "In the document they said..." Including statements of absence of or problems with the facts in the provided documents. 3) Other participants (OTH): the elaboration includes referring back to the opinion from other participants or prior comments in the discussion. This must be an explicit reference, such as "Like what Maria said..." 4) Mass media (MM): the elaboration includes explicit references to the mass media (newspaper, internet, social media, advertisement, etc.)	Sourced evidence: PER: MAT: OTH: MM:	Sourced evidence: PER: MAT: OTH: MM:	Sourced evidence: PER: MAT: OTH: MM:	Sourced evidence: PER: MAT: OTH: MM:
	OPI-RELA	Relating Opinion to Others	Relating: 1) Response (RES): responding to another speaker 2) Agreement (AGR): a signal of support with something a prior speaker said. Signals such as "I agree," "That's right," "Good/ tremendous/ fantastic/ excellent idea." 3) Disagreement (DIS): a statement that signals opposition with something a prior speaker said. Directly signal by "Disagree," "I sort of disagree," "I'm not sure about that," "That's not right." Or also often signal by "well" before proceeding with what is being disagreed with. Many start with "agree," but followed by a "but" statement."	Relating: RES: AGR: DIS:	Relating: RES: AGR: DIS:	Relating: RES: AGR: DIS:	Relating: RES: AGR: DIS:

Opinion stating-2 (contributing a speech act)	V-RES	Verbal Response	Genuine questions (GQ): 1) Statements that place the operator, like "who," "what," "how," etc., before the subject. 2) Statement with rising intonation at the end of sentence. 3) Directive question, "Please give me an example." Other short verbal signals (VS): 1) Continuer: encourage the speaker to continue talking. Examples like "uh-huh," "mum-hmm." 2) Acknowledgement: representing have received the information. (e.g., "right," "yeah") 3) Newsmaker: expression surprise or noticing (e.g., "oh," "really?") 4) Assessment: such as "that's good," "how awful." 5) Completer: finishing the speaker's phrase.	Verbal Response: GQ: VS:	Verbal Response: GQ: VS:	Verbal Response: GQ: VS:	Verbal Response: GQ: VS:
	COMP-B	Competitive Behavior	Interruption: 1) Verbal Interruption (VI): including speaking before another has finished their turn, cutting people off from completing the statements. It can also appear in the form of short phrases or interjections, such as "wait..." "but..." "nah..." 2) Non-verbal Interruption (NVI): including physical or gestural acts that disrupt another's speaking. Examples like raising one hand before another has finished their turn. Waving hands to distract people's attention from the speaker. Making an exaggerated facial expression. Competition: 1) Assertive style (AS): speaking or responding in an assertive or dominant style. 2) Repetition (REP): repeatedly restating their own point. 3) Strong conviction (SC): showing strong conviction with little willingness to change or compromise. 4) Floor holding (FH): monopolize the floor for an extended period of time, without give others the chance to respond or contribute. 5) Rhetoric question (RQ): a question is asked not to seek an answer but to reinforce the speaker's own argument. This includes, e.g., "Don't we want fairness?," "How could anyone disagree with that?" Hard Power Behavior: 1) Offers (OF): such as proposing a deal of exchange to secure agreement. 2) Demands (DE): insisting others take specific action or adopt a position. 3) Threats (TH): using negative consequences or pressure to push others toward agreement. 4) Exit options (EX): expressing withdrawal from the discussion.	Interruption: VI: NVI: Competition: AS: REP: SC: FH: RQ: Hard Power: OF: DE: TH: EX:	Interruption: VI: NVI: Competition: AS: REP: SC: FH: RQ: Hard Power: OF: DE: TH: EX:	Interruption: VI: NVI: Competition: AS: REP: SC: FH: RQ: Hard Power: OF: DE: TH: EX:	

Listening (acknowledging and trying to understand others during a speech act)	NONV-POS	Positive non-verbal response	<p>Positive response:</p> <p>1) Nodding (NOD) 2) Positive emotional expression (PE) 3) Motor mimicry (MM) 4) Other empathic body language (EMB) 5) Gaze (GZ)</p> <p>-- In-person settings: Gaze is coded when the listener turns their face or gaze toward the speaker's face for the required observation period. When seated beside the speaker, direct eye contact is not required. Turning the face of gaze toward the speaker's direction is sufficient to indicate attentiveness.</p> <p>-- Online settings: Gaze is coded when the listener looks directly at the screen and maintains a fixation for the required observation period.</p>	<p>Positive response:</p> <p>NOD: PE: MM: EMB: GZ:</p>			
	NONV-NEG	Negative non-verbal reaction	<p>Negative remotional reaction (NER): including frowning, showing surprise or confusion, displaying fear or alarm.</p>	<p>Negative non-verbal reaction</p>	<p>Negative non-verbal reaction</p>	<p>Negative non-verbal reaction</p>	<p>Negative non-verbal reaction</p>
	NONV-DIS	Dismissive non-verbal response	<p>Dismissive behavior (DB): scoffing, eyerolling, loud sighing, turning body away from speaker, ignoring, focusing elsewhere, talking over</p>	<p>Dismissive behavior</p>	<p>Dismissive behavior</p>	<p>Dismissive behavior</p>	<p>Dismissive behavior</p>

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